

Outer-Sphere Association. Part I Tris(biguanide) Cobalt(III) Salts

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Outer sphere association constants of tris(biguanide) cobalt(III) chloride, bromide, iodide and sulphate salts have been evaluated at 25° and 35° from conductivity measurements. The association constants follow the order : $I^- < Br^- < Cl^- < SO_4^{2-}$. With the help of Bjerrum equation and Stoke's law the sizes of the ion-pairs have also been evaluated, and compared with similar other complexes.

METAL biguanide complexes¹ have been the subject of numerous investigations over the past decades. Of these complexes, tris (biguanide) cobalt(III) is remarkable in more than one way ; it has a very high innersphere formation constant² ($\log K = 54$) being higher than that of tris(ethylenediamine) cobalt (III) ($\log K = 48.69$)³ ; it shows asymmetric transformation of the second order during resolution⁴ ; furthermore the complex shows interesting kinetics and mechanistic behaviour⁵ during acid hydrolysis. In this paper we report on yet another aspect of this complex, namely the outer sphere association constants of its salts $[Co_3(BigH)_3]X_3$ (BigH = biguanide ; X = Cl, Br, I, $\frac{1}{2}SO_4$).

The measurement of electrical conductivity of dilute solution provides a valuable method of studying outer-sphere ion association of inert complexes. The conductance behaviour and ion association of hexammine cobalt(III) chloride, tris(ethylenediamine) cobalt(III) chloride, tris(propylene-diamine) cobalt(III) chloride, in aqueous solution were studied by Jenkins and Monk⁶. In our present study we have discussed equivalent conductivities of tris(biguanide) cobalt(III) chloride, bromide, iodide and sulphate salts in dilute aqueous solution at 25° and 35° in terms of Onsager's theory.

Experimental

Tris(biguanide) Cobalt(III) chloride was prepared by slight modification (H_2O_2 oxidation) of the original procedure⁷. The bromide, iodide and sulphate salts were prepared by metathetic reactions on the chloride salt. These samples were carefully purified by several recrystallisations from conductivity water. They were then dried at 110° to constant weight. The purity of the samples was examined by conventional chemical analysis and spectral measurements. The stock solutions were prepared by dissolving requisite amount of the samples in double distilled water of low specific conductance.

Results and Discussions

Equivalent conductivities, Λ , of cobalt(III) tris (biguanide) chloride, bromide, iodide and sulphate have

been measured at different concentrations at 25°. Λ is then plotted against $C^{\frac{1}{2}}$. An approximate value of equivalent conductivity at zero concentrations $\Lambda^0(\text{approx.})$, is obtained from the above plot. From the value of $\Lambda^0(\text{approx.})$ the theoretical slope 'b' is calculated by means of Onsager's conductivity equation⁸.

$$\Lambda_{\text{Exp}} = \Lambda^0_{\text{approx.}} - [0.7852/Z_1 Z_2 / \frac{q \Lambda^0_{\text{approx.}}}{1+q^{\frac{1}{2}}} + 30.32(Z_1 + |Z_2|) \sqrt{2} C^{\frac{1}{2}}]$$

where C is the concentration in equivalent/lit and $\sqrt{2} C^{\frac{1}{2}}$ has been substituted for $I^{\frac{1}{2}}$ for 3:1 valent salt.

$$\text{Hence } \Lambda_{\text{Exp}} = \Lambda^0_{\text{approx.}} - 'b' C^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

In deriving the values of 'b' the ionic conductivities of chloride, bromide and iodide were taken as 76.34, 78.4 and 76.8 respectively⁹. $\Lambda_{\text{Exp}} + b C^{\frac{1}{2}}$ is plotted against C. These plots are shown in Fig. 1, whereby an accurate value of equivalent conductivity of the salt at infinite dilution, $\Lambda^0_{\text{Onsager}}$, is obtained. Fig. 2 shows that the experimental curve (Λ_{Exp} vs $C^{\frac{1}{2}}$) of $[Co_3(BigH)_3]Cl_3$ lies below the theoretical line, calculated $\Lambda = (\Lambda^0_{\text{Onsager}} - b C^{\frac{1}{2}})$ vs $C^{\frac{1}{2}}$. This difference is attributed to ion-pair formation between the complex cation and the anion. The ion pair is assumed arbitrarily to be a 1:1 complex. This assumption is justified in view of the low association constants obtained. A higher (e.g. 1:2) outer sphere complex will certainly have a very low association constant so as not to influence the association constant of the 1:1 complex to any significant extent. The dissociation constant corresponding to the equilibrium :

$$\text{is given by : } K = \frac{[Cl^-][Co_3(BigH)_3]^{3+}}{[Co_3(BigH)_3 Cl]^{2+}} \dots\dots(1)$$

The experimental solution is taken as a mixture of (i) 3:1 valent salt of molar concentration αm and (ii) 2:1 valent salt of molar concentration $(1-\alpha)m$, where m is the molar concentration of the salt and α is the degree of dissociation of the ion pair.

Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Onsager Extrapolation : (a) $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_3]\text{Cl}_3$
(b) $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_3]\text{I}_3$; (c) $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_3]\text{Br}_3$

Fig 2.

Fig. 2. Conductivities of $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_3]\text{Cl}_3$: upper curve shows calculated $\Lambda (= \Lambda^{\circ} \text{Onsager} - bc^{1/2})$ vs. $c^{1/2}$, lower curve shows $\Lambda_{\text{Exp.}}$ vs. $c^{1/2}$

Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. Conductivities of $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_3]_2(\text{SO}_4)_3$
Under curve shows calculated $\Lambda (= \Lambda^{\circ} \text{Onsager} - bc^{1/2})$ vs. $c^{1/2}$
Lower curve shows $\Lambda_{\text{Exp.}}$ vs. $c^{1/2}$

Then Onsager equation for 3:1 valent salt can be written as :

$$\Lambda_{3:1} = 143.88 - 198.23 I^{1/2} \quad (\Lambda^{\circ} \text{Onsager} = 143.88) \quad \text{and}$$

that of 2:1 valent salt as :

$$\Lambda_{2:1} = 121.37 - 138.52 I^{1/2}$$

where ionic strength $I = (1 + \alpha) C$; C is the concentration in equivalents per lit.

$\Lambda^{\circ} \text{Onsager}$ for the 2:1 ion pair is derived from the relation¹⁰

$$\frac{\Lambda^{\circ} \text{ion pair}}{\Lambda^{\circ} \text{Co}(\text{BigH})_3^{+3}} = \frac{|Z|}{3}$$

where $|Z|$ is the charge of the ion pair namely +2. This equation is obtained from Stoke's law by neglecting the ion size effect on the mobility. This estimation of $\Lambda^{\circ} \text{ion pair}$ is rather arbitrary. But it can be shown by calculation that considerable change in $\Lambda^{\circ} \text{ion pair}$ does not affect the derived values of K , the dissociation constant of the ionpair appreciably.

The solvent corrected specific conductivity of the solution is given by

$$10^3 k = 3\alpha m \Lambda_{3:1} + 2(1 - \alpha)m \Lambda_{2:1}$$

and equivalent conductivity is given by

$$\Lambda_{\text{Exp}} = 80.91 - 92.34 I^{1/2} + \alpha(62.91 - 105.89 I^{1/2}) \dots (3)$$

At first α is assumed to be unity and the corresponding value of I obtained from equation (2) is used in equation (3) whereby a truer value of α is obtained by using equation (2). This process is repeated until constant figures are obtained.

The equation (1) may be written as

$$K = \frac{(2 + \alpha) \alpha m f_1 f_3}{(1 - \alpha) f_2}$$

The results are given in Table 1. The activity coefficients f_1, f_2 and f_3 of Cl^- , $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_3] \text{Cl}^{2+}$ and $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_3]^{3+}$ species respectively are calculated from Debye-Huckel equation : $-\log f_i = -0.509 Z_i^2 I^{1/2}$ where f_i refers to the activity coefficients of the Z_i ions.

TABLE I—CONDUCTIVITY OF CO (III) TRIS (BIGUANIDE) HALIDES AT 25°

$10^4 C$	$10^2 C^{1/2}$	$\Lambda_{\text{Exp.}}$	$\Lambda_{\text{Exp}} + bc^{1/2}$	α	$10^3 K$	Mean Association constant	
<i>Chloride salt</i>							
15.20	3.899	129.7	140.71	0.9401	15.95	55	
13.37	3.657	130.8	141.13	0.9484	16.88		
12.16	3.487	131.3	141.15	0.9491	15.82		
10.94	3.308	132.3	141.63	0.9588	18.13		
9.73	3.119	133.0	141.81	0.9620	17.88		
8.51	2.917	133.8	142.04	0.9663	18.09		
7.29	2.700	134.7	142.33	0.9718	19.07		
6.08	2.466	135.7	142.66	0.9779	20.92		
<i>Bromide salt.</i>							
19.71	4.439	131.5	144.13	0.9456	21.77		34
17.35	4.165	132.7	144.55	0.9537	23.31		
15.77	3.971	133.9	145.20	0.9661	30.02		
14.19	3.767	134.5	145.22	0.9665	27.94		
12.62	3.553	135.6	145.71	0.9757	35.37		
11.04	3.323	135.7	145.15	0.9663	22.56		
9.467	3.077	137.1	145.85	0.9490	32.40		
7.884	2.808	138.2	146.19	0.9849	38.72		
6.308	2.512	139.0	146.15	0.9845	31.09		
4.732	2.175	139.9	146.09	0.9837	22.91		

Table 1 : (Contd.)

Iodide salt.					
10 ⁴ C	10 ² C ^{1/2}	Λ _{Exp.}	10 ⁵ X	10 ⁴ K	Meah Association aconstant
15.20	3.899	132.4	143.36	0.9721	35.70
13.37	3.657	132.5	143.78	0.9795	44.20
12.16	3.487	133.9	143.71	0.9786	39.00
10.94	3.308	134.8	144.10	0.9856	53.69
9.730	3.119	135.2	143.97	0.9837	42.90
8.510	2.917	136.0	144.20	0.9879	51.81
7.250	2.700	136.6	144.19	0.9877	44.60
6.080	2.466	137.4	144.33	0.9900	46.98
Sulphate salt					
14.81	3.848	100.5	12.67	8.29	
13.04	3.611	102.9	10.54	8.3	
11.85	3.442	103.7	9.52	7.87	
10.67	3.267	106.0	8.04	8.04	12.6 × 10 ²
9.482	3.079	107.4	6.95	7.71	
8.296	2.880	110.0	5.63	7.80	
7.112	2.666	112.6	4.45	7.78	
5.927	2.434	115.1	3.45	7.51	
4.742	2.177	118.6	2.43	7.43	

Similar treatments have been applied to tris (biguanide) cobalt (III) bromide and iodide salts. The results are given in Table 1. The relation between the experimental equivalent conductance (Λ), ionic strength (I) of the solution and degree of dissociation (α) for bromide salt is

$$\Lambda_{Exp} = 82.78 - 93.00 I^{1/2} + \alpha (64.22 - 106.71 I^{1/2})$$

and for iodide salt is

$$\Lambda_{Exp} = 81.46 - 92.58 I^{1/2} + \alpha (63.44 - 106.24 I^{1/2})$$

In the case of tris(biguanide) cobalt (III) sulphate Λ^o Onsager's the equivalent conductivity at zero concentration, is obtained by summation of mean limiting conductivity (Λ^o = 68.08) of the cation (obtained from chloride, bromide and iodide salt) and 80 for the ionic conductance of the sulphate. The dissociation constant corresponding to the equilibrium.

$[Co(BigH_3)_3]^{3+} + SO_4^{2-} \rightleftharpoons [Co(BigH_3)_3]^{2+} + SO_4^{1-}$
is given by

$$K = \frac{(2m - x)(3m - x)f_3 f_2}{x f_1}$$

where m is the molar concentration of the salt and x is the concentration of the ion-pair. The relation between the observed conductivity and the calculated conductivity is given by

$$\Lambda'_1 + \Lambda''_1 - \Lambda_{Exp} = \left(\frac{x}{C}\right) (3\Lambda'_1 + 2\Lambda''_1 + \Lambda''_1) \dots (4)$$

where conductivity equations are :

$$\text{for } [Co(BigH_3)_3]^{3+} \dots \dots \Lambda'_1 = 68.08 - 180.5 I^{1/2}$$

$$\text{for } SO_4^{2-} \dots \dots \dots \Lambda''_1 = 80.00 - 166.1 I^{1/2}$$

$$\text{for } [Co(BigH_3)_3]SO_4^{+1} \Lambda''_1 = 22.69 - 60.17 I^{1/2}$$

From equation (4) and ionic strength equation $I = 2.5C - 6x$, by approximating until constant x and I values, the dissociation constant K has been calculated. Fig. 3 reveals a high outersphere association in the sulphate salt compared to that in the chloride salt (Fig. 2).

Same procedure has been adapted for the measurements of association constants at 35°. The relation between the observed conductivity Λ_{Exp}, ionic strength (I) and degree of dissociation of ion pair (α), after taking into consideration the dielectric constant (D) viscosity coefficients of the solvent (η) at 35°, are as follows :

$$\text{for } [Co(BigH_3)_3]Cl_3 : \Lambda = 99.26 - 115.41 I^{1/2} + \alpha(77.97 - 133.13 I^{1/2})$$

$$\text{for } [Co(BigH_3)_3]Br_3 : \Lambda = 100.37 - 115.77 I^{1/2} + \alpha(78.45 - 133.21 I^{1/2})$$

$$\text{for } [Co(BigH_3)_3]I_3 : \Lambda = 99.06 - 115.30 I^{1/2} + \alpha(77.69 - 131.80 I^{1/2})$$

For $[Co(BigH_3)_3]_2(SO_4)_3$, the ionic conductivities of three types of ions are :

$$\text{for } [Co(BigH_3)_3]^{3+} \dots \dots \Lambda'_1 = 84.77 - 227.55 I^{1/2}$$

$$\text{for } SO_4^{2-} \dots \dots \dots \Lambda''_1 = 95.68 - 204.52 I^{1/2}$$

$$\text{for } \{Co(BigH_3)_3SO_4\}^+ \dots \dots \Lambda'''_1 = 28.25 - 75.85 I^{1/2}$$

The outer sphere association constants (Table 1) of the 1:1 ion pairs are of the expected order, and compare favourably¹¹ with those of comparable ion pair reported in the literature. The order :

	I	Br	Cl	SO ₄
Association constant at 25°	22	34	55	12.6 × 10 ²
at 35°	24	37	62	13.2 × 10 ²

exposes the influence of decreasing size and increasing charge of the ion pair forming anion.

Bjerrum¹² from electrostatic consideration gives the relation between association constant of the ion pair and size of the ion as :

$$K^{1-} = \frac{4 \pi N}{1000} \left(\frac{|Z_1 Z_1| e^2}{DK \Gamma} \right)^3 Q(b)$$

$$b = \left(\frac{|Z_1 Z_2| e^2}{a DK T} \right)$$

a = distance of closest approach of the ions forming ion-pair. From the experimental association constant we calculated the values of Q(b) and from the Q(b) values we obtain the values of 'b' from standard table¹³ and hence 'a' can be calculated. Stoke's law in terms of conductivity in aqueous solution at 25° can be written as :

$$a = \frac{9.16 \times 10^{-7} Z}{\Lambda^o_1}$$

where a = radius of ions
 Z = valency of the ion
 Λ_1 = limiting conductivity of the ions.

The distance of the closest approach of the two ions of an ion-pair is assumed to be equal to the sum of Stoke's radii, the value of a derived from Stoke's law may be compared with that obtained from Bjerrum's equation. Expectedly $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_8]^{3+}$ (4.03) (Table 2) is substantially larger than $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6]^{3+}$ (2.77 A°)¹⁵ and is only slightly larger than $[\text{Co}(\text{en})_3]^{3+}$ (3.68 A°)¹⁵. However the value is slightly smaller than the reported size of $[\text{Co}(\text{Pn})_3]^{3+}$ (4.23 A°)¹⁵. Unfortunately the Bjerrum distances did not agree well with those obtained from the sum of the anion radii and the cation radii both being obtained from Stoke's law (Table 2). However such discrepancies have also been noted by Jenkins and Monk¹⁵.

TABLE 2—APPROXIMATE RADII OF $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_8]^{3+}$ AND ION-PAIRS

Cation/ anion	Radius from Stoke's law a (A°)	Ion-pair	Radius from Stoke's law a (A°)	Radius from Bjerrum equation a (A°)
$[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_8]^{3+}$	4.03	$\{[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_8]\text{Cl}^{2+}\}$	5.23	4.28
Cl^-	1.20	$\{[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_8]\text{Br}^{2+}\}$	5.21	6.11
Br^-	1.18	$\{[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_8]\text{I}^{+2}\}$	5.22	7.38
I^-	1.19	$\{[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_8]\text{SO}_4^{+2}\}$	6.32	5.035
SO_4^{2-}	2.29			

Finally with increase in temperature there is a some slight enhancement in the association constant values indicating a somewhat favourable entropy change. Similar favourable entropy changes in respect of outer sphere association has been reported in the literature¹⁶. The explanation possibly lies in the breakdown of the hydration shell of the complex cation and anion thus leading to release of solvent molecules from an 'ordered' state to a state of 'disorder'.

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